

Hello and welcome to another LNL newsletter edited by me, David Smailes, as part of my role as Chair of the Local Network Leads.

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LNL News

First, a periodic reminder that an LNL WhatsApp group exists, and it can be joined via this - <https://chat.whatsapp.com/H6dh6LYJb5O5NkH3lXYrvl> - link.

Also, are you keen to be a bit more involved in UKRN? If so, please get in touch with me - david.smailes@northumbria.ac.uk - if you would like to guest edit an edition of this newsletter, or would like to Chair one of the LNL meetings. A new Chair Elect for the LNL group will be elected later this year, and volunteering for one of these tasks would be a

great way to see if you'd like to take on that role.

LNL Spotlight

This month, I'm nudging you in the direction of this - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A2cqgPlulBg&t=1272s> - talk by me. Apologies that it's a talk from me (but it is only 5 minutes long!). Please let me know if you would like me to share a talk of yours in this section of a future newsletter.

Award Opportunity

The Society for Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology and Evolutionary Biology's Commendation Award is open for nominations. Any initiative that aims to benefit the Eco-Evo community by fostering Open Science values or practices is eligible, and the competition is open until mid-August. See this - <https://www.sortee.org/awards/> - page for more info.

New LNL!

A new LNL - Shames Maskeen - has joined UKRN from Leeds Trinity University. You can find more about him at this - <https://research.leedstrinity.ac.uk/en/persons/dr-shames-maskeen> - webpage.

UKRN Webinar

There's a great-looking UKRN Webinar at the end of the month on 'Checks for Reproducibility'. There'll be three talks on aspects reproducibility checks and wider matters in academic outputs. See this - <https://www.ukrn.org/event/ukrn-webinar-symposium-on-checks-for-reproducibility/> - webpage for more info and to register.

— LIFECYCLE — JOURNAL

External Conferences/Events

The Center for Open Science are launching a new journal (Lifecycle Journal), and they are running a webinar about its aims etc. tonight at 7pm (i.e., April 10th). You can find out more at this - <https://lifecyclejournal.org/> - webpage and you can register here - https://cos-io.zoom.us/webinar/register/9417419788471/WN_mJnfy0aTgG0gHiAez92WA#/registration

Reading Recommendations

Communications Psychology published this - <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44271-024-00179-1> - perspective piece titled 'A manifesto for a globally diverse, equitable, and inclusive open science' back in January and it is very much worth a read.

Closing Remarks

If you would like to contribute, or have something that you think should be shared (especially for the Spotlight section!) please get in touch. We would love to hear from you; it's your newsletter! contact@ukrn.org